

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

TOPICAL CORTICOSTEROID INDUCED HYPER PIGMENTATION -A CASE REPORT

Khevna Shah^{*1}, Nidhi kadakia¹, Hemraj Singh Rajput¹, Disha Patel²

¹SumandeepVidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Vadodara-391760, Gujarat, INDIA.

²Parul Institute of Pharmacy Vadodara- 391760 Gujarat, INDIA.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 06/08/2022

Available online

02/09/2022

Keywords

Hyper pigmentation,
Topical Corticosteroids.

ABSTRACT

Hyper pigmentation is a common skin problem in present days over the world In this condition there is increased in melanin production which ultimately results in darker patches of skins Due to overuse of topical corticosteroids under the influence of friends, relatives unfortunately leads to many adverse effects like hyper pigmentation, hypo pigmentation, striae, and rosacea. Here we describe two cases of hyper pigmentation induced by topical corticosteroids misuse. In case 1 the male patient came with the complaint of skin lesions over body and itching sensation since 5 months. He was using a topical corticosteroid cream (ocovate GM) on advice of para medical staff. In case 2 the 18 years female patient complaint about the skin lesions over body and itching since 4 years. She was using a topical corticosteroid cream Halobrt. On examination they both showed the signs of hyper pigmentation. The patches were significantly improved after the treatment recommended by dermatologist.

Corresponding author

Khevna Shah

Pharm D Intern, Department. of Pharmacy,
Sumandeep Vidyapeeth deemed to be University, Gujarat, India.
khevnashah077@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Khevna Shah et al. Topical Corticosteroid Induced Hyper Pigmentation -A Case Report. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2022:12(08).**

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INTRODUCTION

Topical corticosteroids (TCS) is a great weapon for dermatologist to treat different steroid responsive diseases like lichen planus, vitiligo, psoriasis etc. In present days problem is, there is no proper regulations as a result of these steroids are being supplied over to the counter to unsuspected patients and it lead to harmful and unwanted effects. So these Steroids which are boom are becoming curse. The unregulated and long application of topical corticosteroids without dermatologist supervision leads to several adverse effects like skin thinning, bleeding under skin, growth of unwanted hair on face, striae, hyper pigmentation telangiectasia and hypopigmentation and if potent topical corticosteroids are applied around the eye for long time it can invite disaster i.e. glaucoma (Increase intra ocular pressure). Nowadays common people apply these applications for fairness, acne and as an antifungal medication. Hyperpigmentation is a medical term used to describe a condition in which patches of skin become darker in color in compare to normal skin. Excess melanin production is the most common cause of hyper pigmentation. Melanin is a pigment found in the skin that gives it its colour. Melanocytes, which are skin cells, generate it. The production of melanin in body might be affected by a variety of illnesses or causes. Furthermore, hyper pigmentation occurs as the adverse effect of topical corticosteroids due to prolong usage.^[1,2]

OBJECTIVE

After receiving approval from the institutional ethics committee and permission to collect data, the project was launched. On the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria, the patients were chosen. Patients of all generations who had used TCS for more than 30 days in steroid-sensitive diseases with cutaneous side effects met the inclusion criteria. Patients might be either males or women. Additionally, people who misuse these drugs (not using properly topical steroid on the skin in terms of wrong doing pattern, frequency, duration, or indication). Additionally, those who were on oral immunosuppressive medicine, refused to give consent, or had poor general health were not included in the study. Patients who met the requirements for the trial were given a Patient Information Sheet after being informed about it. Informed

Figure 1: Topical Corticosteroid induced hyperpigmentation. (Male patient).

Figure 2: Topical Corticosteroid induced hyperpigmentation. (Female Patient).

CASE REPORTS

CASE -1

A 32 years old male presented to superspecialty hospital with the complaint of skin lesions over body and itching sensation since 5 months. He was using a topical corticosteroid cream ocosvate GM (CLOBETASOL+GENTAMICIN+MICONAZOLE) on advice of para medical staff. Moreover, similar complaints were observed in his father. Due to long term use of topical steroids the symptoms get worsen. On examination he showed the signs of hyperpigmentation on abdomen and groin area. Apart from this, he has never taken any parenteral steroids or oral steroids Routine lab test where done nevertheless it was normal. Skin scraping were also done and did not reveal any fungal filaments. The patient was advice to apply onabet cream (sertaconazole), capsule syntran (itraconazole 100mg) for 30 days and tablet avil (pheniramine) for 10 days. He was also counselled and instructed about the adverse effects and proper usage of topical corticosteroids.

CASE -2

An 18 years old female presented to Dhiraj hospital with the complaint of skin lesions over body and itching since 4 years, amenorrhea since 2 years. She was using a topical corticosteroid cream Halobrt (Halobetasole Propionate cream 0.05% w/w) for more than three times a day on advice of some friends/ relatives for tinea infection. Furthermore, similar complaints were observed in her brother. Due to long term use of topical steroids it lead worsen the symptoms resulting in adverse effects. On examination she showed the signs of hyperpigmentation in inner thighs. She was diagnosed with tinea cruris. Besides this, she had never taken any oral or parenteral steroids. Routine lab test where done and the results were normal. The patient was properly counselled and given advice about proper usage of topical corticosteroids and harmful effects of misusing it. She was further advice to apply candid cream (clotrimazole), capsule itradeep (itraconazole 100mg) for 30 days and tablet avil (pheniramine) and tablet cetirizine for 10 days.

DISCUSSION

Many dermatological problems benefit from the use of topical corticosteroids. They've been licenced by the FDA for the treatment of inflammatory and pruritic dermatologic disorders. Diffuse hyperpigmentation can be caused by a variety of factors. Medications and metabolic reasons are two of the most common. When addressing a patient, especially one with dark complexion, it is critical to thoroughly document the time, onset, and duration of symptoms by history and physical examination. People frequently try a variety of treatment options and home remedies without consulting a dermatologist. In present days patients, take treatment suggestions from their relatives and friends instead proper dermatologist. They tend to continue the improper treatments for a very prolong period of time and present to dermatology OPD after worsening of their skin condition. The prevalence of hyperpigmentation is also been reported in few studies done by Jha et al, [2] Bhat et al, [3] Manzoor et al [4] Steroid use is frequently linked to depigmentation. In the above scenario, topical corticosteroid has been misused over 1 year. Patient presented to the OPD with hyperpigmented patches on the groin area.

Their skin had significant thinning as the result steroid ointments penetrate far deeper than as compared to other body parts, hence showing early signs of hyper pigmentation than other body parts. Although hypo-pigmentation is a common adverse effect of topical corticosteroids but hyper-pigmentation is also reported as adverse effects after TC misuse over six months.

Nowadays facial hyperpigmentation is also a persistent concern among the younger generation. The underlying causes of facial hyperpigmentation must be addressed for successful treatment. Patients should be urged to seek consultation from a dermatologist for their hyperpigmentation issues rather than using topical corticosteroids without consulting a proper dermatologist.^[3,4]

CONCLUSION

The most significant initiatives to reduce the misuse of topical corticosteroids is to inculcate the dangerous effects of misusing/overusing the topical steroids and to create awareness among general public about the use of the drugs through various educational programs and campaigns. Apart from this, government should impose law and restrict the easy availability of topical corticosteroids over the counter.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The Authors would like to thanks the Department of Pharmacy Sumandeep Vidyapeeth University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

ABBREVIATIONS

TCS -Topical Corticosteroids

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